

SROTODUSHTI IN HYPERTENSION: AN OVERVIEW**Dr. Astha Negi^{1*}, Dr. Ruby Rani Agarwal²**

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ABSTRACT

According to Ayurveda, *Purusha* is assumed to be made of innumerable *Srotas*, which are responsible for performing all the physiological and functional activities. *Srotas* is defined as “*Sravanata Srotamsi*” meaning the structure through which *Sravanam* takes place. *Srotas* (body channels) play a crucial role in the transport of substances throughout the body. Each *Srotas* is responsible for the movement of specific *Dosha*, *Dhatu* (tissues), and *Mala* (waste products) *Srotodusht* is the condition of *Srotas* which is susceptible to pathological changes to produce a disease. Here we will understand vitiation of *Srotas* in Hypertension. Hypertension is not directly mentioned in Ayurvedic texts but we can apply Ayurvedic Principles to understand disease mechanism. The WHO ranked Hypertension as one of the leading causes of premature deaths worldwide. Considering its high prevalence and to explore its

relation with different *Srotas* an attempt is made here to assess the role of *Srotodushti* in Hypertension.

KEYWORDS: *Srotas*, *Srotodushti*, *Dosha*, Hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

“As rightly said by *Acharya Charaka*, a physician should not be embarrassed if he is unable to name a disease, as each and every disease can't be named “. This quotation here fits in today's era where new diseases continue to sprout everyday. Hypertension is one of them.

Although Hypertension is not explicitly mentioned in Ayurvedic Texts we can apply Ayurvedic Principles and concepts to understand the condition so it is essential to acknowledge the value of both traditional and modern approaches, integrating them to create a comprehensive understanding of health and disease. In Ayurveda, understanding the disease process (*Samprapti*) involves analyzing various features including *Dosha*, *Dushya*, *Srotas*, *Adhithana* etc. Here focusing on *Srotas* in Hypertension and their *Dushti* can provide valuable insights into the disease mechanism. *Acharyas* mentioned different types of *Srotas*. *Acharya Charaka* has given 13 *Srotas* while according to *Acharya Susruta* there are 11 *Yogvahi Srotas*. Here we will explore Hypertension from *Srotodushti* perspective and by applying Ayurvedic Principles.

SROTAS

Srotas are the channels of circulation which carry the transforming tissues from one place to another places. The term *Srotas* is derived from the Sanskrit root “*Sru Sravane*” meaning to exude, to ooze, to flow, to filter. *Acharya Charaka* has defined *Srotas* as “*Sravanata Srotamsi*” meaning the structure through which *Sravanam* takes place. Those from which flow of the body substances takes place or those through which the materials flow in the body are called *Srotas*.

SROTAS SWAROOPA

The structures of *Srotas* are similar to respective *Dhatus* but they are present in different shape and size, such as circular, thick, micro, long and spread in the whole body like as branch of creepers etc.

SROTODUSHTI SAMANYA HETU

Those *Aahar* and *Vihar* which have similar properties of *Doshas* and are opposite to that of *Dhatus* are responsible for *Srotodushti*. In other words it is the *Dooshana* (contamination) of *Srotas* caused by food and activities which are similar to that of *Dosha* and opposite to that of *Dhatus*.

SROTODUSHTI SAMANYA LAKSHANA

Excessive activity of *Srotas*, obstruction, formation of glands in *Srotas* or dilatation of *Srotas* which forms gland, movement of *Srotas* contents other than natural pathway or channels are four different types of *Srotodushti Lakshana*.

HYPERTENSION

The definition of Hypertension according to World Health Organization (WHO) is systolic blood pressure values of 140 mm of Hg or more and diastolic blood pressure values of 90 mm of Hg or more. Blood Pressure is defined as the lateral pressure exerted by blood against the wall of arteries. The etiology of Hypertension involves the complex interplay of environmental and pathophysiological factors that effect multiple system, as well as genetic predeposition. Hypertension is the silent killer of mankind as most sufferers(85%) are asymptomatic.

Types of Hypertension

1. Primary Hypertension- Also known as essential Hypertension. Its tends to be familial and is likely to be consequence of an interaction between environmental and genetic factors.
2. Secondary Hypertension- It is less common and has different underlying causes including endocrine diseases, kidney diseases, heart diseases etc.

DISCUSSION

As we highlighted *Srotodushti* study on hypertension, the *Samanya Lakshan* or general symptoms of vitiation of body channels could be of 4 different types- *Atipravritti* (excess activity), *Sanga* (obstruction), *Sirogranthi* (formation of glands in *Srotas* or dilatation of *Srotas* which forms gland), *Vimargagaman* (movement of *Srotas* contents other than natural pathway or channels). For every disease manifestation, vitiation of *Srotas* is necessary. *Atipravritti* of *Srotas* in Hypertension could be due to increased activity of *Vyaan Vata* which leads to increased force of blood and thus increased cardiac output resulting in Hypertension. Excess activity of *Raktagata Vata* also plays a role in Hypertension.

Sanga of *Srotas* refers to obstruction in the channels where blood flows, which can be directly co-related to atherosclerosis and coronary artery diseases where plaque build up in artery walls resulting in narrowing of blood vessels – a key factor to increase blood pressure. *Sirogranthi* is the formation of knots, swellings or nodular structures in the *Sira* (channels). These nodules, tumours or occlusions effects the blood flow and hence raise blood pressure. *Vimargagaman* of *Srotas* in context of Hypertension could be understood as a result of its complication where increase in blood pressure can leads to diseases like epistaxis, brain hemorrhage etc in which blood moves out of its normal passage. So the pathological process in any disease often involves the *Dushti* (vitiation) of one or more *Srotas*.

CONCLUSION

Srotodushti is a key concept in Ayurveda referring to the vitiation or malfunctioning of body channels and plays a key role in disease mechanism. Hypertension showcases the timeless truth expressed by *Acharya Charaka*: not all diseases need name to be understood or managed. The Ayurvedic approach—by focusing on *Dosha*, *Dushya*, *Srotas*, and *Samprapti*—offers a rich, multidimensional understanding of complex modern disorders like hypertension. *Srotodushti* plays a significant role in understanding hypertension through the lens of *Ayurveda*. By understanding *Srotodushti* and its relationship to Hypertension, Ayurvedic Practitioners can develop personalized treatment plans to address the root causes of Hypertension and promote overall health. Steps taken in managing Hypertension could be *Nidana Parivarjana*, *Shodhana*, *Shamana Chikitsa* etc. By integrating classical Ayurveda Principles with contemporary understanding the assessment of *Srotodushti* continues to offer profound insights in any disease mechanism. Hypertension can be understood as *multisrotas* disorder where by balancing *Dosha* of particular *Srotas* and by tailoring interventions based on vitiation of *Dosha*, a state of well being can be achieved.

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